

REPORT

Ukrainian HEIs' response to the humanitarian and societal crisis

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Deliverable Factsheet

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List of abbreviations

The following list presents the acronyms used in the deliverable in alphabetical order.

<i>Abbreviation</i>	<i>Meaning</i>
HE	Higher Education
HEI	Higher Education Institution
IDP	Internally Displaced Person

1. Project summary

This publication is a result of the Erasmus+ AGILE project (“Higher education resilience in refugee crises: forging social inclusion through capacity building, civic engagement and skills recognition”, <http://www.agileproject-erasmus.eu/>), whose aim is to increase the resilience of HE systems to address the ongoing needs of refugees through social participation and skills recognition.

The AGILE project aims to enrich HE curricula by proposing new pedagogical designs that encourage grassroots and digitally enhanced actions in both formal and informal learning environments.

The project is coordinated by the University Paris 8. The consortium is made up of six universities (University Paris 8, Bordeaux Montaigne, University, University of Hamburg, University of Ljubljana, Lviv Polytechnic National University, Kaunas University of Technology), one think-tank (Polish Rectors Foundation) and one business partner (Web2Learn) specialised in open recognition systems and social learning.

1.1. Executive summary

The new phase of the war between Ukraine and Russia, the occupation of territories, the destruction of infrastructure and housing, the loss of human capital force the Ukrainian academic community to reconsider the role of universities, to determine their purpose (mission) and functions (directions of activity) during the war and post-war recovery in the broader context of the formation and development of a knowledge society.

In the state of war unleashed by Russia against Ukraine, not only the liquidation of Ukrainian statehood, but also the physical destruction of the Ukrainian people and their identity was under threat. Ukrainian society is consolidating, as this is the basic guarantee of its self-preservation. The demand for social responsibility in it is significantly increasing. This requires domestic universities to strengthen proactive and reactive social responsibility. In the conditions of the war, the need for the implementation of social projects and programs is sharply increasing, both to preserve the integrity and ensure the functioning of HEIs, and to maintain the vital activities of the communities to which they belong. The state of war in society deeply worsens the conditions for ensuring the proper quality of HE, which is a basic component of the social responsibility of universities. It is also obvious that in conditions of crisis, in periods when society is undergoing significant trials and transformations, the social role of HEIs is growing. This is especially clearly visible now in Ukraine, in the conditions of war. The social role of Ukrainian universities is no less critical at the stage of post-war reconstruction of Ukraine (Балджи, Власова, Калашнікова, Ковтунець, Литовченко, Оржель, Рябченко, та ін., 2022, р.28-30).

Since February 24, 2022, more than 7.2 million Ukrainians have left the country as refugees, and a third of the population has been internally displaced. Among the internally displaced persons are many teachers and students of higher education institutions. These people could become victims of various terrible events that seriously affected their mental and/or physical health, they could lose relatives or loved ones, housing, all their material savings, work, place of study. IDPs need material, financial, socio-pedagogical and psychological help and support. At the same time, they face complex challenges, as they have to cope with the stress of being forced to relocate and adapt their lifestyles to new conditions in an environment of uncertainty.

This report presents an overview of the capabilities of the Armed Forces of Ukraine in overcoming the humanitarian and social crisis, which is accompanied by the forced mass displacement of the population inside the country from dangerous regions close to the contact line to more protected places far from the front. Universities contribute to the social adaptation and social inclusion of IDPs by increasing the social responsibility of universities, which, in turn, represents an opportunity for social development in all its diversity of spheres of influence, such as organizational, educational, research, social, etc. The conducted activities and research were carried out within the framework of work package 4, Activity 6, aimed at expanding existing knowledge and practices regarding how Ukrainian higher education institutions contribute to overcoming the humanitarian and social crisis.

2. General introduction

The analysis of the European documents "Advisory Group 1 on Social Dimension" and "BFUG Working Group on Social Dimension" shows that one of the main principles of strengthening and expanding the social dimension of HE in the European Union is institutional governance, management and policies to expand the opportunities of students and academic staff of the university (Advisory Group 1, 2020; BFUG Working Group, 2022).

Since the beginning of the war in Ukraine, on February 24, 2022, more than 7.2 million Ukrainians have left the country, becoming refugees, and a third of the population has been displaced. The war was in the center of media attention from the first minute, so it quickly gained global publicity, affecting not only Ukrainians, but also people all over the world. It is a well-known fact that war has numerous negative psychological consequences for all (Балджи, Власова, Калашнікова, Ковтунець, Литовченко, Оржель, Рябченко, та ін., 2022, р.67).

During war or any disaster, in some places thousands of people become victims. They may be separated from their families for a time, their homes and educational institutions may be destroyed. The urgent task for the community is to create a safe haven, restore educational institutions and other elements of social infrastructure. It can be assumed that certain HEIs which are restored (or not affected) may be optimal places to hold classes, not only for their students and academic staff, but also for the rest of the society and the whole community nearby. During the war, both children, teenagers, and adults can repeatedly become victims of various terrible events, which can cause severe impact on their mental health. They may witness artillery shelling and shooting, watch the destruction of their hometown or village, or even their homes. They may have to face and witness wounded or dead people, torture and murder, sometimes in large number (mass death of people). They may experience severe losses, see their family members and friends injured or die. They can also be injured themselves. Such an experience can and does lead to various psychological pathologies.

Among the documents that make it possible to understand the level of needs of academic communities and the available resources of HEIs in the context of a humanitarian crisis, there is an Analytical Note prepared by the Brookings Doha Center - the foreign representative office of the American analytical center Brookings Institution in Doha, Qatar. In this document, the authors of the note raise two important and closely related issues about the provision of protection and asylum to displaced teachers and students, as well as the conditions for their return. The first issue concerns the strengthening of the role of international institutions with a mandate to protect refugees and forcibly displaced persons, such as UNHCR20 and the International Organization for Migration (International Organization for Migration, 2023). The second is to unite the efforts of international agencies, donors, and national governments with the aim of creating powerful regional structures for the protection, rescue, return and reintegration of scientific and pedagogical workers; this should be helped by the creation of a regional platform, dialogue with the participation of international organizations and experts, removal of barriers to academic mobility, recognition and accreditation, expansion of employment opportunities (Barakat, Milton, 2015).

After February 24, 2022, HE in Ukraine faced many challenges, including:

1. Damage and destruction of infrastructure, premises of HEIs, loss of educational and research equipment.
2. Significant losses of HE personnel, the contingent of applicants/students who are forced to move to safer regions of the country and abroad (including to study abroad).
3. A decrease in the potential for the formation of state orders in the coming years due to a significant reduction in the number of education seekers, since in the post-war period a large part of student / student youth, high school students, and teachers may not return to Ukraine, remaining outside its borders.
4. Narrowing of the base for conducting educational practice as a result of the curtailment of the work of educational and production plants (centers, complexes, etc.) and leading Ukrainian enterprises.
5. The need for reorientation in personnel training due to radical changes in the personnel needs of the national economy and social life, which dynamically arose during the war and will arise in the post-war period, will be determined by further government decisions and actions.
6. The need to overcome the existing shortcomings (management, legislative, financial and material, methodological, institutional, etc.) of the reform of HEIs, associated with the lack of proper coordination in the field of adult education, the need to improve the results of training of HE personnel by strengthening the coordination of the theoretical component of training with labor market requirements (Шкарлет, 2022, p.167).

The ongoing armed aggression of the Russian Federation against Ukraine has threatened the lives and health of all citizens of Ukraine. In order to create a safe educational environment for participants in the educational process from regions where active hostilities are ongoing, in particular Donetsk, Luhansk, Kherson, individual communities of Zaporizhzhia and Kharkiv regions, as of August 1, 2022, according to the operational information of the Ministry of Education and Culture, was moved (from taking into account the first wave of displacement in 2014) 29 HEIs and 64 separate structural subdivisions of HEIs of state, communal and private forms of ownership. During the period from 2014 to the beginning of the 2022-2023 academic year, 134 HEIs were relocated in Ukraine due to war and aggression by the Russian Federation, which is 11.7% of their total number in the country (Шкарлет, 2022, p.165)

In March 2022, the majority of such institutions carried out the educational process remotely or were in the stage of relocation, transfer of students to vacation mode, temporarily undecided on the process of resuming work or did not provide information. As of March 15, 2022, only 62 institutions, or 21.5%, of 289 HEIs provided information; by the beginning of April 2022, the situation had changed for the better - information had already arrived from 37.5%. 54 HEIs of those that provided information in mid-March of the current year conducted their main activities in distance, 6 - in mixed, and 2 - in informational and advisory forms of education; at the end of March – 81, 6 and 0 HEIs respectively. Regionally, the largest number of HEIs that switched to distance learning on both of these dates were located in Kyiv and Odesa region. Among the HEIs that were relocated after 2014, and forced to change their location again in 2022, are Melitopol State Pedagogical University named after Bohdan Khmelnytskyi, Tavria National University named after V.I. Vernadskyi, Pryazovsky State Technical University, Donbas State Pedagogical University, Kherson State University, Donetsk National Technical University, Mariupol State University,

Berdiansk State Pedagogical University, Vasyl Stus Donetsk National University, Taras Shevchenko Luhansk National University, Volodymyr Dahl East Ukrainian National University, etc. (Шкарлет, 2022, p.184).

In accordance with the order of the Ministry of Education and Culture of Ukraine "On some issues of organizing the work of institutions of vocational pre-university and higher education during martial law" dated 07.03.2022 No. 235, an institutional basis was created for taking measures to ensure the protection of participants in the educational process, employees and property of educational institutions; carrying out, if necessary, the evacuation of participants in the educational process; provision of special study conditions (establishment of an individual study schedule, provision of academic leave, etc.) for those seeking education who are in the ranks of the Armed Forces or territorial defense units, are engaged in volunteer activities. In addition, legal conditions were formed for the evacuation and relocation of military personnel from occupied territories and territories where active hostilities were taking place. During the war period, more than 110 orders of the Ministry of Education and Culture were issued on these issues (Шкарлет, 2022, p.175).

From the point of view of the preservation of the intellectual capital of Ukraine, temporarily displaced HEIs are primarily thousands of internally displaced scientific and pedagogical and other workers who have lost their property and are currently in difficult living conditions, do not have the opportunity to fully communicate, and often do not have information about the fate of members family, friends, acquaintances, which, of course, is reflected in their psycho-emotional state, but at the same time, they strive to establish the educational process in a new place and maintain a contingent of students, ensure the success of the admissions campaign and high-quality training of specialists (Мазур, 2023).

Staff turnover is characteristic of all displaced HEIs, because their main scientific and pedagogical staff are resettlers, whose life plans during the period of residence and professional activity in a new place "became not much clearer for themselves in the conditions of lack of their own housing, family circumstances, war, which continues... At the same time, the labor teams are actively replenished with local educators at various levels: from professors and teachers of the departments to the management of the university" (Дмитрик, Сервачак, 2020). That is, there are processes of bilateral integration of scientific and pedagogical workers in a completely new competitive environment. An increase in the share of local educators in the personnel composition, changes in the number of students cause the representatives of displaced universities to worry about the loss of their own identity, formed mainly on the regional features of the development of HE, changes in the nature of corporate culture (Курило, Савченко, Караман, 2019). Temporarily displaced HEIs and internally displaced scientific and pedagogical workers need additional social protection tools and special support and assistance in resuming full-fledged activities from host communities, local self-government bodies, the government and international organizations.

Ukrainian HEIs initiate social events or initiatives (currently humanitarian, psychological and organizational assistance) to internally displaced persons, assistance to the military and representatives of the territorial defense, informational support of the country at various sites against Russian aggression, informing employees and students about possible projects, etc. («Inspireurope Recommendations: Expanding opportunities in Europe for researchers at risk», 2022). The European Association of Universities initiative emphasizes the importance of HE, the creation of global and national programs for researchers, and cooperation with public organizations, especially in wartime. It is noted that universities can be an integral part of the creation and operation of national programs to support researchers who continue work during the war, thus demonstrating to politicians the benefits of international scientific

exchanges. By cooperating with public organizations and other structures, universities can create national networks (universities can be an integral part in the setup and development of national support programs by showcasing their commitment to supporting researchers at risk, and informing policy makers about opportunities and benefits resulting from welcoming international talent. In collaboration with other institutions and NGOs, HEIs may also establish national networks and structures. This document also emphasizes the term "researchers at risk" - scientists who "experience threats to their life, freedom or research career, as well as those who have the status of displaced persons due to such threats. While some at-risk researchers have been granted refugee, displaced person or similar protection status, there are scientists in need of assistance from civil society organizations specializing in the protection of scientists who are outside the refugee process, seeking or holding temporary visas or work permits through visiting, research/scientific positions at host universities in Europe or other countries outside their own country" («Inspireurope Recommendations: Expanding opportunities in Europe for researchers at risk», 2022).

2.1. Internally displaced persons in Ukraine

Internally displaced persons (IDP) are already included in the group of internal migration caused by uncontrollable factors, such as natural disasters, military conflicts, and others. Being in a de facto state of war, Ukraine faced the problem of forced migrants. Due to the lack of similar precedents in the past, the normative and legal framework of Ukrainian legislation did not contain relevant provisions regarding the regulation of the above-mentioned phenomenon. Among the numerous problems currently faced by Ukraine, the phenomenon of forced migration is not only a consequence of the military conflict, but also acts as an indicator of Ukrainian society's readiness for crisis situations. At the same time, forced migration in Ukraine is one of the vivid examples of the consequences of emergency situations that lead to a humanitarian crisis.

For the first time, the problem of IDPs appeared before Ukraine after the Russian annexation of Crimea (03.2014) and the unfolding of the conflict in part of the territory of Donbas, from where approximately 1.5 million people were forced to relocate. These territories were named "temporarily occupied" in Ukrainian legislation (2014-2015). A new, much stronger wave of forced resettlement was caused by the full-scale invasion of Russia (February 24, 2022). As hostilities continue, the bombing of populated areas continues, part of the territory captured by the enemy is de-occupied, so the number and composition of IDPs are constantly changing, but the very problem of the situation with IDPs remains for a long time. The consequence of internal displacement is a sharp break in social, cultural, professional, interpersonal ties, loss of material stability, which can lead to social deviations, surge in criminal activity and psychological problems of individuals and groups. In order to avoid negative social manifestations of forced resettlement, it is necessary to create conditions for a non-traumatic and harmonious entry of social subjects into a relatively new social and cultural space for them.

Forcedly displaced persons (IDPs) need material, financial, socio-pedagogical and psychological help and support. The situation of constant stress caused by the forced departure from the permanent place of residence, disruption of stability and the usual state of life, loss of breadwinners, friends, relatives, deprivation of parental care has a negative effect on the personality. This situation is most acutely perceived by children who are psychologically sensitive to traumatic situations.

As of mid-June 2023, 4,871,807 internally displaced persons have been registered, of whom 60% are women, 40% are men. One in five registered IDPs (21.6%) is a child under the age of 17. The same percentage is made up of persons older than 65 years. The war forced even 700 people aged 100 and over to leave their homes [The number of Ukrainians and their migration abroad due to the war. Ukrinform. 2023. October 22. URL: <https://www.ukrinform.ua/rubric-ato/3732355-kilkist-ukrainciv-ta-ih-mig...>]. However, according to officials' estimates, the real number of IDPs is higher, since about 2 million citizens, although they were forced to relocate, but for various reasons did not register as IDPs.

2.2. Humanitarian and social crisis: features of the Ukrainian experience

As a result of the military operations, the challenges of the humanitarian crisis, which most affect IDPs and other vulnerable groups – the elderly, people with disabilities, women and children, have been actualized. Such challenges require an urgent solution, because the situation of people from vulnerable groups in a war situation can get worse and worse. In addition, the number of IDPs may continue to grow and, accordingly, the humanitarian crisis will deepen. IDPs, who often belong to other vulnerable groups, not only face unprecedented challenges in finding shelter and building their lives from scratch, but also have to overcome obstacles related to bureaucracy and a lack of access to necessary resources (jobs, education, medicine). These circumstances prevent their return to a full-fledged life through reintegration into communities in new conditions (Shevchenko, 2023).

Most of the Ukrainian studies devoted to IDPs and the humanitarian crisis are related to legal and economic aspects. A significant amount of research is related to social rehabilitation and adaptation. This issue was studied by Ukrainian scientists such as T. Semigina, O. Rasskazova, H. Slozanska, I. Albul, I. Zhrebko, N. Kolyada, O. Kravchenko, M. Mishchenko, A. Popovych, M. Skochko, K. Chupina and others. Social adaptation of IDPs was studied by N. Mazina and N. Skok and others. Among foreign studies, the study of the social and economic consequences of mass migration of people due to conflict is widespread (Muggah, 2003). Separate studies focus on the challenges associated with access to aid in war zones. Thus, R. Goodman analyzes the problems of humanitarian access and strategies for its provision in the conditions of a military conflict (Goodman, 2006). Another direction is the analysis of the impact of the humanitarian crisis on vulnerable groups. Thus, H. Bankoff examines how crises affect various vulnerable groups (Bankoff, 2001). O. Pyschulina, V. Yurchyshyn, K. Markevich and others analyze the impact of the humanitarian crisis on the socio-economic situation in Ukraine (Pyschulina, 2022). In this context, J. Guénette, F. Kenworthy and K. Wheeler examine the economic losses and challenges for the recovery of Ukraine, considering the global impact of the humanitarian crisis on the world (Guénette, Kenworthy, Wheeler, 2022). However, there are significant gaps in research on the impact of the humanitarian crisis on internally displaced persons and other groups in the context of military operations in Ukraine. In particular, the reaction of Ukrainian institutions, in particular HEIs, to the humanitarian and social crisis is not sufficiently presented.

Different definitions of humanitarian crisis are used in the international community. Although the Geneva Convention (1949) is a key document of international humanitarian law, it does not contain a definition of the term "humanitarian". A humanitarian crisis is a serious disruption of the functioning of a community or society, causing large-scale human, material, economic or environmental losses that exceed the ability of the affected community or society to cope with the use of its own resources, which requires an application for external assistance at the national or international level. A disaster situation can be caused by a person (for example, an armed conflict) or a natural phenomenon (for example, a drought) (Ramesh, Frison, Warren, Smith, Hossain, Knight, et al., 2014, p. 15). International law and the theoretical and methodological base of international organizations also do not contain a general definition of the signs of

humanitarian crises, a description of their variety, duration or intensity. At various times, international organizations have used the terms "complex humanitarian emergencies" or crises and "complex situations". A "complex" or "complex" crisis means that such situations are not purely natural, but have components that indicate human influence and continue over a long period of time. These are social crises that affect groups of people with varying degrees of vulnerability and resilience.

A. Natsios identified the following signs of a humanitarian crisis: 1) deterioration or complete collapse of the central government and (partially) civil society; 2) armed conflicts (often between ethnic or religious groups) and massive violations of human rights; 3) episodic lack of food security, which often turns into mass hunger; 4) macroeconomic collapse associated with hyperinflation, mass unemployment and a net reduction in GDP; 5) mass movements, the appearance of displaced persons and refugees fleeing the conflict or in search of food (Natsios, 1996, p. 67).

In the Ukrainian context, it is important to take into account the following signs of a humanitarian crisis: a) the presence of significant human suffering and death, b) environmental destruction, c) weakening of state institutions and systems (health care, education, etc.), d) limited opportunities for aid delivery. In addition, there are signs of a global (or complex) humanitarian crisis in Ukraine, which is characterized by the need for large-scale, multifaceted humanitarian assistance, obstacles or the prevention of humanitarian assistance due to political and military restrictions, significant risks for the safety of humanitarian workers in some areas.

Humanitarian crises during military operations are characterized by the presence of a significant number of challenges. Challenges, in the context of humanitarian crises, are any serious trends, shocks or the development of certain negative phenomena that may have global consequences and thus shape humanitarian needs and change the environment in which crisis actors will operate in the near future. One of the main challenges is solving the problems of IDPs.

According to official government data, as of the beginning of 2023, almost 4.9 million IDPs were registered in Ukraine. The International Organization for Migration in Ukraine provides data on 7.1 million IDPS (Report on Internal Displacement in Ukraine, 2022). More than 8 million people have become refugees (OCHA Situation Report, 2023). This is one of the most numerous waves of internal and external migration in the world. By comparison, European countries took in around one million refugees from Africa and the Middle East in the 2015 wave and up to 4 million refugees during the Yugoslav wars of the 1990s.

2.3. Understanding Ukrainian HEIs' reaction to the crisis

The majority of IDPs come from the East and South of the country - 67% (about 3.4 million people) and 17% (about 867,000 people), respectively. In particular, 25% come from Kharkiv Oblast, 21% from Donetsk Oblast, 10% from Zaporizhia Oblast, 10% from Kherson Oblast, and 7% from Luhansk Oblast. IDPs from the mentioned regions found shelter all over Ukraine, but most of all - in the city of Kyiv and Kyiv region (9% and 9%, respectively), Kharkiv (14%) and Dnipropetrovsk (12%) regions.

The problems associated with mass forced resettlement require significant efforts from the state, communities of settlement and origin / return to adaptation, integration / reintegration of affected persons and their social support. At the same time, IDPs face complex and multifaceted tasks, since in conditions of uncertainty they have to survive the stress of a forced change of residence and adapt their lifestyle to new conditions.

Within the implementation of the Erasmus+ project AGILE "Higher education resilience in refugee crises: forging social inclusion through capacity building, civic engagement and skills recognition" (Erasmus+ KA2 program - potential development) on March 8, 2024 by the teachers of the Department of Sociology and Social Work Klos L.Ye., Klymanska L.D., Herasym H.Z., Kozak M.Ya. an online focus group was organized and conducted with the involvement of internally displaced persons who are studying advanced training courses in the specialty "Social Work" at the Lviv Polytechnic National University.

The purpose of the focus group was :

- first, to find out the needs and problems of IDPs in Western Ukraine, to identify the main needs and problems that arise during the integration of IDPs in the host communities;
- secondly, to determine and discuss the potential of social work (in particular, at the OP "Social Work" of the National University "Lviv Polytechnic" in providing social integration, determine the potential of social work in solving the problems of IDPs in host communities;
- thirdly, to identify opportunities for adult education, in particular, advanced training courses for social work specialists organized on the basis of Lviv Polytechnic National University.

The topic of the focus group discussion concerned the evaluation of the potential of social work in the process of adaptation of forcibly displaced persons in a new place, in particular, using the opportunities of adult education. It should not just be a period of adaptation, it should be a period of adaptation with social support, support groups, circles, social workers, psychological help.

Informants were guaranteed full confidentiality. The participants agreed to a video recording of the focus group. The report contained quotes in an impersonal form. Problems of interaction with the local population, emotional state of IDPs, access to services and resources were discussed. When organizing a focus group with refugees from the east of Ukraine who moved to the west of Ukraine, it was important to focus on their experiences, feelings and adaptation to the new environment.

Figure 1. *Online focus group with the involvement of IDPs, who are studying advanced training courses in the specialty "Social work" of the Lviv Polytechnic National University.*

Several issues were formulated for discussion:

About adaptation to a new place. About interaction with the local population:

- What are the relations with local residents?
- To what extent is there support from the local community?
- What are the cultural and social differences between the East and the West of Ukraine?
- What is there in the west of Ukraine that needs special attention in the process of adaptation of IDPs in a new place?
- To what extent, do you think, do IDPs feel secure in their existence right here, in the west of Ukraine?

About the emotional state of forcibly displaced persons:

- What factors affect the emotional state of immigrants?
- What are the biggest challenges faced by IDPs in everyday life here?
- Is there anything that, in your opinion, IDPs particularly like or dislike in their new place of residence?

About access to services and resources:

- From your point of view, how sufficient is the access to necessary resources and services (for example, housing, food, medical care, education)?
- What specific needs can you name that are not being met at the moment?
- What kind of help or support do you think would be most helpful at this time?
- Are there any resources or services that IDPs would lack?

The conclusions that can be drawn based on the analysis of the transcript of the focus group discussion can be grouped around three topics:

1. the most pressing problems during resettlement;
2. fault lines/conflicts between IDPs and the local population;
3. proposals for mitigating the situation.

- 1. The first is the most acute problems of IDPs during resettlement.** Among the most acute is the housing problem.

The problem of finding housing: poor conditions in places of short stay

"We contacted the hotline in Ivano-Frankivsk about providing us with at least temporary housing, but we were refused, because they said that we should contact the organization, maybe they have shelters, so housing was our first such need." It is especially difficult for elderly people, people with children, and people with disabilities to stay in such conditions.

"Institutions for short-term stay of people, such as schools, cultural institutions, are generally unacceptable for people. I saw how such institutions are organized. These are just school mattresses. Even if for a short time, it's like another hard labor for them - spending the night on these mattresses with the child, if it's still a breast child, then it's generally..."

"People come in shock, and living together is a scandal. Kindergartens and schools are very difficult. When

you are already emotionally and psychologically broken, plus all the people are gathering, it is very difficult. People immediately tried to find a place to live separately."

"There was a period when we were leaving, there was a curfew in Odesa for 3 or 4 days, that is, we wouldn't make it there, we wouldn't make it somewhere further, conditionally, to Ternopil either, we stayed in Kropyvnytskyi for the night, that's the format in kindergarten - okay But if, for example, it will be there for a month or more, as in Drohobych, people live there for a year, in kindergartens, in schools. It's terrible."

Modular towns built for IDPs cannot be considered a way out of this "housing problem". *"That is, if it is about the fact that people need to be accommodated for some more or less long term, then they simply collapse. A person should have personal space, even for this short-term period. About these modular individual residences. It seems to me that in order to integrate into the community, to look for a job there, to understand in general where you will be there, you need to communicate with local people, and if it is some town in a remote place, where you sit with your family, do not go out anywhere, do not see anyone - then actual integration will not take place"*.

Lack of housing for rent

Exaggerated housing rental prices. Landlords in conditions of excessive demand, especially in large cities, inflate rental prices. If the price is moderate, then the living conditions are bad. The cost of apartments in Lviv, Frankivsk is higher. The IDPs themselves see a negative in this – the desire of the locals to profit from the problems of the IDPs. The price of housing for immigrants is clearly overestimated *"If earlier in Ivano-Frankivsk apartments were cheaper than in Kherson, now they are three times higher"; "In cities where there is a lot of work and it is different - housing prices are high, in places where housing is cheap and it is available - there is simply no work."*

The problem of the psychological state of people after forced displacement

"It seems to me that a person is left without his acquaintances, his usual circle of communication, without what a person is used to, with whom it is comfortable to spend time. That is, this is such a change, this is my vision", "... psychological help was provided to the child... because I was very worried about the child, because active hostilities were going on in our country and the occupation at the same time, that's why we applied. He went to my place there for 2.5 months for drawing, they had such trainings."

The period of adaptation should also include psychological assistance to IDPs, so that this time is used with benefit and really helps people get used to new conditions and integrate into the community. *"Our psychologists are currently working with refugees around the world. When at first you are confused, without anything, stressed, then of course you are in the position of a child. You should get all the help you need, because you are in an unusual situation, you have lost a lot, you have to start from scratch. But gradually, as adults, we all have to grow up a little. When you have mastered yourself, the environment, and seen new opportunities, you can already earn something yourself. You should be supported on this path. But it is very bad if people are kept in this infantile position: that we will give you money endlessly,*

because you can't do anything. But I don't know how much we can talk about it now. The war is not over yet. Perhaps it is too early to talk about the termination of payments to IDPs. As we move into the restoration and rebuilding phase, then maybe we can expect something from each other."

Figure 2. Discussion continues during an online focus group involving IDPs

According to respondents, the availability of psychological assistance in short-term accommodation locations is extremely important. Individual informants also note that living in modular houses is, in their opinion, PTSD prevention, because it is here that displaced persons have the opportunity to "be together". *"I would like to add that the help of psychologists is very necessary in such towns - I am talking about modular, where there are many people, it is very cool and they are really needed."* *"We need good conditions, separate accommodation for the family. From psychological world practice, for people who have left hot spots, they must arrange centralized residences, where they can all be together. Where they are united by the same problems, they have the same grief. This is PTSD prevention. These are good conditions and compact living."*

The problem of the circle of communication - common experience unites

As a rule, IDPs communicate in their circle - *"in general, my circle of communication is those people who share with me problems with housing, with education, with worries about parents, about home... A*

common circle of communication is, after all, internal displaced persons.... For example, I am from Kherson, my acquaintances are from Zaporizhzhia, and we have not communicated before, these are not even my places, but simply they are also internally displaced persons, that is, I contact local people purely on such institutional issues as with organizations." Instead, communication with representatives of local communities is important for solving the problems of IDPs. But for certain reasons, according to informants, it happens at a very low level, or it does not exist at all. There was an opinion that in some communities the authorities are not interested in the integration of IDPs, do not perceive them as equal residents of communities. If integration takes place, it is mainly due to the IDPs' own desire and mostly with the help of local activists, volunteers and public organizations.

"I didn't feel any integration at all... There are no meetings or trainings. They have a so-called "skhodka" for locals, they solve problems with water, with meters and so on, why don't they collect for IDPs? Why don't they want to hear their problems? I'm not saying to solve everything right away, at least listen to what we need! Maybe I don't need a job, but seeds for the garden and that's all. There are such issues that can be easily resolved at the local government level! It is possible to attract volunteers, active residents - there would be a desire. There is only one public organization, I thank them very much, but not the authorities - they are a big minus... Why so? Because people are used to living like this, they have responsibilities, and IDPs are an additional burden, completely unnecessary."

"We are like the fifth wheel. This attitude is unpleasant", "The authorities said at the meeting that we should deal with our local people, and you are an IDP. They don't want us to integrate too much here. But some people will have nowhere to go back to, they will have to stay here. The city government is not involved in the development of any documents or solutions, only volunteers need us. We are here with funds from volunteers and public organizations."

"I have the impression that the local authorities do not know that we exist here. If there was some kind of communication, communication, interaction, it would be easier for us, and it would be good for them. We are ready to work, to communicate. And so there is no communication, no cooperation, no vision. In our kindergarten, there is such a group as a national team: both local and IDPs. And they found a common language among themselves. In the same way, adults, if they were grouped together, they would also find a common language and it would be wonderful."

- 2. The second theme is the theme of fault lines between IDPs and members of the host community.** It is about potential causes for conflicts. During the detailed discussion at the FG, it was possible to single out three main areas where conflicts may occur: everyday life; clash of different cultures and identities; giving or receiving help.

Household issues

Conflicts on the background of household issues are the most widespread, but the least intense: they are

easier to resolve than others. This type of conflict most often arises between migrants and their host communities. The most common place of conflict is the place of a compact settlement, and the reason is almost always the difference in habits and the vagueness of the rules of residence, which should be stable and understandable for everyone. Informants pointed to the following reasons for conflict situations: comments from owners due to excessive and uneconomical use of water and other communal services; comments from the owners due to the difference in household habits, approaches to cleanliness and cleaning.

The local population is more sensitive to violations of the "rules of conduct" by IDPs. There are phrases that "they are worse educated than we are" and others. However, there is a gradual penetration of habits, so the level of culture is leveled over time.

Clash of different cultures

The cultural characteristics of immigrants may differ from those of the host community. Different habits, traditions, religious preferences and language of communication can cause conflicts. The IDP received many positive comments about the religious and folk traditions of the residents of Western Ukraine, the religiosity and human qualities of local residents, as well as the entrepreneurship of local residents, the development of small and medium-sized businesses. The conflict "East - West" - *"this is the tradition of celebrating religious holidays, that is, you don't always know all these subtleties... sometimes the local population reacts differently to this ignorance: someone can tell you correctly, someone looks at you askance, someone makes such remarks not very pleasant"*.

In a negative context, from the very beginning of the conversation, IDPs mentioned misunderstandings and conflicts on linguistic grounds — they often received remarks from the residents of the host communities about speaking in Russian, as well as using surzhik (elements of two or more languages, combined artificially, without following the norms of the literary language) or Russianisms. Language is the most frequently mentioned cause of conflicts. It is about the Russian language and the language of hostility. A breakdown in a relationship - a language problem - *"with language this is a problem"*; *"we ran into each other in the park when the children heard the child speak half Ukrainian and half Russian (he learns Ukrainian at school, but at home in Kherson we all spoke Russian), so it was a little difficult for the child to switch immediately, but we were learning Moms they took away the children, and the children simply called the Muscovite..."*; *"I applied to one school and when the principal immediately started asking me questions - how does the child speak... Well, I said that we will not go to school. We stayed to study remotely at our school. He insisted that the child must speak Ukrainian language"*.

The IDPs did not like the desire of representatives of local communities to teach Ukrainian language to the immigrants. *"We will teach you the Ukrainian language - "I faced the fact that the first question was that we will teach you the Ukrainian language. I say thank you, but I speak Ukrainian well, I say mistakes there... but you don't need to teach me, I will learn Ukrainian myself. "*

The IDPs themselves explain their attachment to the Russian language with historical reasons - *"Unfortunately, unfortunately, historically it happened that the west of Ukraine was under Austria-Hungary, but the people preserved the language a little. Although there are still a lot of Polish words and*

allusions... And we have allusions from that (Russian) side..."

Sometimes a dispute starts because of a preconceived negative attitude towards a person, which is not supported by facts, where stereotypes prevail over reality. IDPs are stigmatized. It consists in imposing negative traits on a certain segment of the population and accusing it of having such traits. Some FG participants shared their experiences of negative attitudes toward them. In their opinion, local residents have stereotypes about IDPs, which often become the cause of discrimination.

Even where the IDPs spoke Ukrainian, a stereotype is reproduced - all Easterners speak the "incorrect" Ukrainian: - *"We switched to Ukrainian before the child started speaking)...but still, when we came here to the kindergarten, I spoke with the teacher in Ukrainian, we just came to get to know each other in the group, she told me "We only speak Ukrainian"... and it became so unpleasant for me. It's like I'm saying that... Well, they haven't even heard the words yet, but this has already started a language problem. I also think about those children who spoke Russian from an early age, well, that was the environment they had... Well, why not take them to kindergarten, kick them out..."*

"In Western regions, there is a stereotype that all Easterners speak Russian. I was often asked where I was from. I say: "I'm from Rasin." "Why do you speak Ukrainian?". I say: "I live in Ukraine." For some reason, they formed the opinion that all Orientals are really Russian-speaking."

Another stereotype was reproduced in the FG discussion – the stereotypical attitude towards the displaced people – they are all the same, they should be given everything for free and without queues. They described the situation when an IDP woman turned to a dentist *"she had a toothache, her cheek was swollen. She went to a doctor here in Frankivsk beforehand, to a doctor she had already seen, she also had two teeth removed, so he knew her. She was in such acute pain, and she ...couldn't make an appointment. And when she came, he began to raise her - what is not accepted in our country, you are already the sixth immigrant today who came from the south without a record..."*.

Probably the most terrible for everyone was the stereotype - if it were not for the Russian-language war, there would be no war. In fact, the accusation of eastern Russian-speakers is that the war started because of them. *"If it weren't for the Russian speakers, this war wouldn't have happened. You yourself have led to this..."*

Another area of conflict is the provision or acceptance of aid

This conflict zone is associated with a lack of resources and a sense of injustice. Due to financial difficulties, any help is a valuable resource. Conflicts arise on the basis of its distribution. The issue of employment is more pressing. It is interesting that both resettlers and representatives of the receiving communities say about this problem. Misunderstanding is caused by giving preference to internally displaced people over local residents, and vice versa.

3. Finally, the third topic that was raised in the discussion is the proposed ways of solving the problems of IDPs

The mechanism for improving the situation, according to the informants, is the establishment of a dialogue between local people and IDPs with the help of joint activities, useful for the community, and

any activity in general.

"It is necessary to tell more local people the stories of IDPs living in the community: successful, unsuccessful, different. Formats: living library, educational activities. Reaching more of the target audience in the community will be more beneficial. Even the village council is less involved in helping IDPs than volunteers."

One of the directions of this work is informing

Informing the community about the problems and needs of IDPs, and on the other hand, informing IDPs about the rituals, traditions, and ceremonies of the local community. In general, respondents rate the level of information as low.

"Information at the level of zero. How did it happen that I found a side job? In the summer, we signed up for classes on psychological relief for children. We registered with the Red Cross. Among the volunteers was the director of the resource center, with whom we spoke. She offered me a job. We have already all gotten to know each other here: Donetsk region, Kherson region, Luhansk region. No one works with information systematically."

According to some informants, the low level of informing the community about the problems and needs of IDPs and vice versa - IDPs about the problems of the community, is due to the reluctance of local authorities to accept new residents to the community. The format of posting information does not always meet the needs of target audiences. *"Sometimes there is some information on their official page, but a 75-year-old grandmother can't find it, she doesn't know how. And this village - the Internet disappears! Or there is no light! That is, there is no feedback at all with the authorities! But even if you hang information on a pole, people will inform each other, word of mouth works. They must be pulled, the mass media must be involved, it must be done so that they show their activities."*

Information about vacancies and possible places of work will be very important for informants. The informants themselves proposed to create a "base" where data will be entered that will help both parties: IDPs will be able to find work, and the community, for its part, will be able to accept the right specialist. Also, according to some informants, it is advisable to launch a Telegram channel in which every IDP can monitor the availability of vacancies in the community.

"Telegram channels. Channels have been created that inform about various things. If all this were fully working, then you could create a channel for IDPs. There are people of various professions here: economists, teachers, manicurists. People could find some kind of work to live more or less decently".

Public organizations play and should continue to play a powerful role in the integration of IDPs in host communities. *"We integrate only through a public organization, through volunteers. The following trainings take place: they invite a psychologist, they invite coaching, we ask what is needed on some topic. Integration courses were held. We participate. My child here goes to an art school, participates in all competitions based on public organizations, the state does not participate. These are all public organizations. Local authorities are cooperating, but it is very difficult. The city council says that "we are*

not on time, we have other issues." If you are more sociable, you get to know the same locals and integrate faster."

"I think that mainly public organizations and volunteer organizations should help in socialization and integration. That is, not only the government. The authorities can really provide some facilities there, can encourage, but all this should be, in my opinion, more volunteers, organizing all this".

"There are messages periodically in the city's chat about where you can come, there is a children's space where you can come, so that there are free classes with children, things like that, but, in my opinion, these are either volunteer funds or donor funds. I was here at the literary evenings for everyone, the events are held for everyone - not divided, whether they are local or not. I made many acquaintances among the locals."

Another way to integration is to independently and gradually establish communication with everyone who can help IDPs: *"I have fully integrated. The first is advice for all visitors, you need to be a resident of the city where you settled. You can't say "your IDP" that I'm a displaced person, and everyone owes me. This immediately begins opposition, they stop understanding you. And when you start to explain your problems in normal human language, they come to meet you and help you. You don't need to shout: "Give it to me".*

"If you show that you can do something and that you can help with it, the authorities at all levels will gladly take advantage of it. It is possible to integrate, in principle, and also benefit the community. Everything depends on a person's desire and his skills".

The problems of IDPs identified during the focus group may have solutions thanks to the participation of the university - the fulfillment of a social function. And in the end, some of the identified problems, as the experience of Lviv Polytechnic shows, were solved precisely thanks to the active participation of the University. First of all, regarding the first block of problems related to the settlement and adaptation of IDPs in a new place. The most pressing problem of IDPs - settlement - was one of the first responses of the University to the "wave" of refugees, IDPs. In particular, for the urgent needs of IDPs who were heading to the western border of the country and used Lviv as an intermediate stop before crossing the border with Poland, Hungary, Romania, Moldova, Slovenia, Lviv Polytechnic already in the first weeks and months of the war allocated several educational buildings for the arrangement of shelters for refugees and IDPs. In the corridors and auditoriums, conditions were created so that people could rest, sleep, warm up, receive warm clothes, warm food, bedding, hygiene products, satisfy hygiene needs, receive psychological support, consultations on transfer to the border or within the region, and on social protection issues.

Almost immediately after the full-scale invasion, student dormitories were allocated, which began to accept IDPs for a longer period of time - weeks and months. To this day, some of the student dormitories remain at the disposal of IDPs who decided to settle in Lviv. There are all the conditions necessary for a normal, full-fledged life. Following the example of Lviv Polytechnic, other universities in Lviv and Western Ukraine also operated. In particular, in Ivano-Frankivsk, Lutsk, Ternopil, Rivne, Chernivtsi. Among the IDPs who still live in the dormitories of Lviv Polytechnic are also teachers who got jobs at the National University "Lviv Polytechnic" as their main place of work or on a part-time basis. Their main place of work remains their universities, in particular, the Hryhoriy Skovoroda Kharkiv National Pedagogical University, the Taras Shevchenko Luhansk National University.

With the beginning of the full-scale invasion, Lviv Polytechnic, in particular the Department of Ukrainian Language, initiated free Ukrainian language courses for all those wishing to improve their conversational level. The courses were organized in a hybrid format – interested IDPs could participate in face-to-face meetings, and, if they chose, could join online meetings.

Another aspect of the University's assistance to IDP teachers and students, as well as the wider IDP community in Lviv and Lviv region, was the organization of socio-psychological assistance in the form of counseling, in particular in the Social Council of the student campus. An important part of the University's work in promoting the social adaptation of IDPs is the use of adult education. In particular, the organization and conduct of advanced training and professional retraining courses for IDPs in order to facilitate their employment in a new place. In this way, assisting IDPs in obtaining a permanent source of income, improving their financial situation, and promoting professional and social adaptation in new conditions.

2.4. Ukrainian universities under martial law: addressing challenges of the humanitarian crisis

Universities are a place for learning for representatives of different age groups - as students in the traditional sense, young people, tau and students with professional experience. They offer professional development courses, certificate courses for acquiring a new specialty, for example, for war veterans returning to civilian life or internally displaced persons. The latter receive vouchers for training from the Employment Centers in the places of new residence. No less important part of the activity of universities is scientific work, research. Research results are presented at scientific and scientific-practical conferences. Scientific research is an important tool for bringing together both experienced scientists and young scientists and researchers, including students.

International conferences are an example of using research activities as a tool for rapprochement and inclusion, as well as a way to share achievements in topical issues. In particular, in May 2024 (May 9-10), the Department of Sociology and Social Work of the Lviv Polytechnic in partnership with universities of Ukraine (Kharkiv National University named after V.N. Karazin, Institute of Sociology of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine, Ivan Franko National University of Lviv, National Technical University Kyiv Polytechnic Institute, Mykolaiv National University, Uzhhorod National University and foreign universities (Naval Academy in Gdynia, Poland) of Applied Sciences in Berlin, Germany; University of Würzburg, Germany, University of Manitoba, Canada). The "IDPS AND REFUGEES IN THE CONDITIONS OF WAR: PROBLEMS AND REALITIES" section worked as part of the conference.

Figure 3. Conference program page, section 4

The session allotted for the work of the sections. Two moderators worked on the session Larysa Klymanska – doctor of political sciences, professor (Lviv Polytechnic National University), Roman Borisov - candidate of sociological sciences, associate professor (Kharkiv National University named after V.N. Karazin). In total, we presented 8 reports, in which the speakers touched to varying degrees on the problems of forcibly displaced persons and refugees in the conditions of war.

Part of the reports was based on the empirical material of the authors. What is valuable is that these are the latest materials, these are materials from studies that are not yet completed.. In particular, the report of Roman Borysov, associate professor, candidate of sociological sciences (Kharkiv National University named after V.N. Karazin) **"Educational trajectories of Ukrainian refugee school children: factors, barriers, opportunities"** was based on the research that is still ongoing and was devoted to the education strategies that parents choose for their children, mainly mothers, forced to stay in other countries. The research is conducted in a qualitative sociological paradigm. On the basis of the preliminary analysis, four strategies will be derived, which are chosen depending on several factors - the decision to return to Ukraine, the child's existing language skills, and the prevailing circumstances. Among these 4 strategies, the strategy of transnationalism, which assumes that families with children continue to move from their first country of residence, was of particular interest. The information about the so-called adaptation classes and the principles of their formation and functioning was quite interesting for me. The report of the Candidate of Sociological Sciences Svitlana Shevchenko (Institute of Sociology of the NAS of Ukraine) was interesting and informative.

"Ukrainian military migrants in Poland: two years after 24/02", in which Ms. Svitlana demonstrated the situation that is developing in our neighbors in connection with the appearance of not just labor migrants from Ukraine, but military migrants. In fact, today there is a situation with two different social groups in Poland. One is those people who emigrated to Poland before the war and went through a rather difficult period of adaptation to the new society. The second is mainly mothers with children who came here forcibly because they were fleeing the war (the researcher called these families and their approach to staying in Poland "child-centric" - they stay in Poland because the children need to finish their education). Ms. Svitlana's attention was focused on the complications that arise for a researcher who wants to study the life of this new group of war migrants: from the search for informants (Svitlana gave an example of the statement of a woman who suited all the parameters for the study, but refused to participate in it - "I don't want to participate in the research, I want my child to forget all the horror we experienced") before determining the status of these women (married, divorced, civil marriage, etc.). Another problem discussed during the conference concerned the desire to return to Ukraine (the counteroffensive plans in the summer generated desires and dreams of returning, but the situation at the front changed and the return had to be forgotten).. In the conclusions, a call was made not to consider the representatives of this community as a "piece cut off from Ukraine", it is rather a resource that is still undervalued, but it is there.

The speech of our colleague Ulyana Yatsyshyn **"The role of education in the integration and adaptation of forcibly displaced persons in Ukraine"** was devoted to the issue of adult education. And it was again

Figure 4. Work of section 4 in online format. Present speakers are students of the Department of Sociology and Social Work of the Lviv Polytechnic: Karina Osiianenko is an IDP (moved from Kherson), Elizaveta Shazhko is a refugee in the Czech Republic.

about education and educational problems, only now for adults. In fact, Ulyana talked about what teacher in Ukraine are doing now. Classes are being held for those who are improving their qualifications under the educational program "Social Work". And, it seems, some of the students are internally displaced persons. The figures given are that out of 1,200 registered IDPs in the Lviv region, 46 took advantage of the opportunity to receive education under the voucher system. A natural question arises - why? After all, as is known, employment centers deal with vouchers, and one of the main problems of migrants is the problem of employment. Obtaining a new qualification is a chance to get a job.

Figure 5. Alla Koval, a professor at the Protestant University of Applied Sciences in Berlin (who emigrated from Ukraine in the early 2000s due to the economic crisis) and her students Sophie Geiger and Judith Müller, who study the problems of Ukrainian refugees in Germany, took part in the work of the section

Three students - one from Poland - spoke at the session of the section. Paulina Zaborowska (Maritime Academy in Gdynia). These are senior partners. Paulina spoke with a message about the role of the media in shaping public opinion about migrants in Poland. She compared the media image of migrants from the East and Ukrainian migrants. The conclusion is that the positive image of the Ukrainian migrant is also the activity of the mass media.

The messages from two students from the Protestant University of Applied Sciences in Berlin turned out to be quite interesting and unexpected. The reports were prepared under the guidance of Alla Koval, Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor of the Department of Social Work at the Protestant University of Applied Sciences in Berlin.

2.5. Ukrainian HEIs response to societal needs

From May to October 2024, questionnaires were sent to university students from the eastern regions of Ukraine, temporarily occupied by Russian troops or located in close proximity to the contact line or active hostilities. The sample included students who moved from Donetsk, Zaporizhia, Mykolaiv, Luhansk, Sumy, Kharkiv, Kherson, Chernihiv and settlements located in these regions of Ukraine. The sample of students from the eastern regions of Ukraine was 400 people. The questionnaire was anonymous. During this time, 40 students answered the questionnaire. Of them, 42.5% previously lived in large cities, 50% - in small ones, and 7.5% - in rural settlements (Fig. 6).

Where did you live before moving to Lviv?

40 answers

Figure 6. *Where did you live before moving to Lviv?*

65% completed their studies in high school, 10% entered the Lviv Polytechnic after college, the rest of the students previously studied in a gymnasium, a specialized lyceum, a general secondary school of grades I-III, studied in another higher education institution - 1-2% each (Fig. 7).

Where did you study before entering the LP NU?

40 answers

Figure 7. In which educational institution did you study before entering Lviv Polytechnic National University?

To the question "What was your motivation for studying at the NULP?" the majority answered: to receive education in the state form (72.5%) and "to continue studying at a prestigious higher education institution" (52.5%).

What was your motivation to study at NU "LP"?

40 answers

Figure 8. What was your motivation for studying at the LPNU?

One of the indicators of successful adaptation of IDPs is the expansion of the circle of communication. We received the following answers to the question "Describe your circle of communication in Lviv" (Fig. 9): 40% have enough friends and acquaintances at the new place of residence and study, 37.5% communicate with students of their group and neighbors in the dormitory. This indicates a fairly high level of student contact. The remaining 15% have not yet found friends at the new place of study and residence, 5% are

in contact with the same immigrants as them, 2.5% do not communicate with people.

Describe your circle of communication in Lviv

10 answers

Figure 9. Describe your circle of communication in Lviv

The next question actually leads directly to the problems of students who moved from the eastern regions - "How significant were the following problems for you when you moved to Lviv" (Fig. 10): finding housing, finding sufficient material means for living, finding a job (part-time job), switching to Ukrainian in communication language, adapt to the local cultural environment, communicate with local residents, prejudiced attitude towards oneself.

How significant were the following problems for you when moving to Lviv?

Figure 10. How significant were the following problems for you when you moved to Lviv?

The most difficult to solve were the problems with finding housing, finding material means of living, and finding a job. In contrast to the opinions expressed at the focus group, the least painful students called "transition to the Ukrainian language" and "prejudiced attitude towards themselves".

Judging by the answers, students received help in solving problems, mainly from relatives, old friends, new friends and acquaintances, turning to the social services of the city and region. And these answers indicate an unused resource in solving problems – the university administration and trade union organizations.

Instead, problems remain. In response to the question "Assess how important it is for you now to provide for the following needs,": students confirmed the relevance of financial assistance, psychological assistance, the need for education and the organization of cultural leisure. This is exactly what the university could take on.

At the same time, to the question "Who helped/is helping to solve problems?" (Fig. 11) the answers were distributed to a greater extent in favor of relatives and friends among the immigrants, the next in terms of ability to help were the social services to which the students turned, and the relevant structures of the university (administration, professional unions, etc.). Even fewer answers were in favor of "new friends and acquaintances found among Lviv residents", as well as friends from the university and old friends.

Who helped (helps) solve problems

Figure 11. Who helped/is helping to solve problems?

Evaluating the degree of urgency of solving the main problems, we received answers regarding the priority and the high level of need for financial assistance.

To the question "How was your adaptation in a new environment?" 72.5% of respondents noted that they do not experience any particular difficulties in the process of adaptation.

How was your adaptation to the new environment?

40 answers

Figure 12. How was your adaptation in a new environment?

The overall assessment of the adaptation of students from the eastern regions is positive. "*I do not always understand the local socio-cultural environment*" - 15% turned out to be a problem area in the process of adaptation. And the university can also help in solving this problem.

Simultaneously with the survey of IDP students, a survey of teachers - representatives of the academic community, scientific and pedagogical workers, who were also forced to leave their place of permanent residence and work in connection with the military operations in Ukraine, starting in 2014, was conducted. The sample included 40 teachers who are IDPs and worked at the time of the survey at Lviv Polytechnic National University, Lviv, Taras Shevchenko Luhansk National University, Poltava, Kharkiv National Pedagogical University named after G.S. Frying pans, Kharkiv; Vasyl Stus Donetsk National University, Vinnytsia, Volodymyr Dahl East Ukrainian National University, Kyiv; Donetsk National Technical University (DonNTU), Drohobych.

Nine teachers took part in the survey. Among the respondents were teachers who are foreign nationals and work at Lviv Polytechnic National University, Lviv, Taras Shevchenko Luhansk National University, Poltava, Kharkiv National Pedagogical University named after H.S. Skovoroda, Kharkiv.

The respondents worked before moving to Kharkiv National University of Radio Electronics, Kharkiv, Kharkiv National Pedagogical University named after H.S. Skovoroda, Kharkiv, Eastern Ukrainian National University named after V. Dalya, Luhansk, Luhansk National University named after Taras Shevchenko (Luhansk), Luhansk National University named after Taras Shevchenko (Starobilsk), Kherson Regional Lyceum, Kherson.

Circumstances that caused internal displacement: 2014, the beginning of the conflict, security, a full-scale invasion of Russian forces, the occupation of the native city of Luhansk. Regarding the time of moving from home to the current place of residence and work, a third of the respondents left their native homes in the spring of 2014, the rest - with the beginning of a full-scale invasion, February-March 2022.

To the question "*How long do you plan to stay in this place of residence?*" more than half of the respondents plan to stay here, another quarter - until the end of the war, the rest either for 1 year or undecided (Fig. 13)

How long do you plan to stay in this place of residence?

9 answers

Figure 13. How long do you plan to stay in this place of residence?"

All respondents indicated that they have been working at their current place of work for more than 1 year. Eight out of nine respondents have a scientific degree, all continue to work in their field.

To the question "*In what position do you work now?*" answered: in the same position as before 5 people, I hold a higher position than before 3 people, I hold a lower position than before 1 respondent. That is, it can be stated that the policy of promoting the professional self-realization of scientific and pedagogical workers from among IDPs is mainly implemented in the host universities (Fig. 14).

In what position do you work now?

9 answers

Figure 14. In what position do you work now?"

The vast majority of respondents (8 out of 9) work in a new place at their main place of work, only one person is part-time.

Regarding the motivation for moving to the current place of residence, a significant majority chose the answer "to be in a safe place" -- 7 out of 9 respondents (77,9%); a third of the respondents had friends and acquaintances, relatives (3 people) (Fig. 15). This provides a clear explanation of the needs of IDPs - first and foremost, security. This also indicates that the vast majority of IDPs have suffered a negative impact on their mental health and need sensitive and attentive treatment and understanding to maintain their mental health at an appropriate level.

Figure 15. What was your motivation for moving to your current location?

Among all those interviewed, only 1 had a target referral from the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine for employment at a new place, the rest received support from their fellow scientists, with whom they had long-standing work contacts. That is, we can say that in such critical and crisis conditions, universities acted as institutions open to scientists and teachers of IDP's.

Regarding the social circle of IDP teachers at their new place of work, most of the interviewees (5 out of 9) answered that they have enough new friends and acquaintances at the new place, while 4 out of 9 do not yet have new friends here. That is, the issue of establishing communication and interaction in a new place is relevant for IDP teachers.

In their free time from work, the respondents mostly deal with family and household affairs, which is understandable in situations where IDP academic workers have moved with their families. Domestic issues are part of the problems they face in a new place. Two out of nine respondents noted that they are engaged in social activities in the institution where they work, and one is engaged in volunteer, community activities.

The biggest problem during resettlement was finding housing (for 4 out of 9), finding sufficient material means of living (2 people), finding a job (part-time job) for 2 people. That is, material and household problems, especially the housing issue, are a significant part of the concerns of IDP teachers. At the same

time, switching to the Ukrainian language in communication, adapting to the local cultural environment or communicating with local residents did not pose significant obstacles for IDPs in a new place. None of the interviewees noted or indicated the prejudiced attitude of local residents towards immigrants. That is, there were no mental complications in the process of adaptation of IDP teachers.

To the question "Do you need any help now?" four respondents (slightly less than half) answered that they do not need any help, they are fine (Fig.16). At the same time, housing remains a problem for a third of the respondents, and two need psychological support. This, in our opinion, could be decided at the university level, perhaps in the labor team or in the relevant services of the university.

Figure 16. Do you need any help now?

IDP teachers, like most students, receive help in solving their problems mainly from old and new friends, some received help from social services. University structures that could help solve the problems of IDPs actually provided help to only one respondent. The interviewees noted that the help provided by the university consisted of material support (2 people), psychological support (1 person), help with housing (1 person). At the same time, 5 respondents (more than half) noted that they did not receive any help from the university at all.

At my new place of work (faculty, department, unit of higher education), I feel the attitude of my colleagues
9 answers

Figure 17. At the new place of work (faculty, department, unit of higher education) I feel the attitude of my colleagues ...

All respondents noted that at their new place of work (faculty, department, unit of the Higher Education Institution) they feel the favorable attitude of their colleagues (Fig. 17). When asked whether the respondents maintain contacts and connections with their old place of work, colleagues, all confirmed such interaction.

The last question related to interaction with the local community: "*Would you like to get involved in cooperation with the local community?*" (Fig. 18). The answers were distributed as follows: 55.55% already cooperate as much as possible or want to do so; 44, 45% did not think about it or have no desire to do it. That is, the IDPs themselves are active in integrating into the host community, but this is a personal choice of each person.

Would you like to join the cooperation with the local community?
9 answers

Figure 18. Would you like to get involved in cooperation with the local community?

3. Lviv Polytechnic National University response to the crisis

Since the beginning of the Russian-Ukrainian war in 2014, Lviv Polytechnic National University has been an active participant in the process of integration of internally displaced persons and participates in various actions to support IDPs and help refugees.

Settlement, housing assistance

Teachers and students joined the placement of forced migrants already on February 25, 2022. In the first months, two locations of IDP accommodation worked: in the first educational building - the IDP Day Stay Center, the main task of which was to accept the night load of newly arrived IDPs, and in the buildings of the Department of Physical Education in In Stryskyi Park - the Center for permanent stay of IDPs, which is still functioning. During the entire period of operation of the Permanent Residence Center, the total number of people who came and lived there was about 1,500 people. We have created acceptable long-term living conditions for them, starting with soft furnishings and ending with an additional heating/air conditioning system. Since there are a significant number of children among the residents of the Center for Permanent Stay of IDPs, various social and cultural events were also organized for them (<https://lpnu.ua/news/prorektor-roman-korzh-pro-zrostannia-rivnia-korporatyvnoi-kultury-universytetu>).

Assistance in employment and university admission

Dozens of teachers and hundreds of young people from various regions of Ukraine, primarily from the east, from the Crimea, and from the south, who have the status of IDP's became employees and students of the Lviv Polytechnic. The university operates in accordance with Ukrainian legislation, according to which all IDPs have benefits in connection with studying at a higher education institution. According to the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine, there are more than 80 thousand internally displaced students in Ukraine ([chrome-extension://efaidnbmnnnibpcajpcgclefindmkaj /https://mon.gov.ua/storage/app/media/zagalna%20serednya/serpnevakonferencia/2022/Mizhn.serpn.ped.nauk-prakt.konferentsiya/Inform-analitic.zbirn-Osvita.Ukrainy.v.umovakh.voyennoho.stanu.22.08.2022.pdf](chrome-extension://efaidnbmnnnibpcajpcgclefindmkaj/https://mon.gov.ua/storage/app/media/zagalna%20serednya/serpnevakonferencia/2022/Mizhn.serpn.ped.nauk-prakt.konferentsiya/Inform-analitic.zbirn-Osvita.Ukrainy.v.umovakh.voyennoho.stanu.22.08.2022.pdf)). More than 550 IDP's students study at the Lviv Polytechnic.

Material support and social scholarship for IDP students

Students of HE colleges with the status of IDP's can count on financial support - a social scholarship, if they study on the budget on a full-time basis. Its amount is UAH 1,180 per month. Such support is provided to students under the age of 23. Payments are stopped if the student is not studying well, has academic debt or takes an academic leave of absence.

To receive a social scholarship, a student must contact the dean's office or group supervisor. He will be offered to write a statement in the name of the rector regarding the provision of monetary payment. A photocopy of the IDP certificate must be attached to the application.

Transfer to vacant budget places upon admission. Applicants who did not pass the budget in the "first wave" upon admission to the university can transfer to vacant budget places, if there are any left after

enrolling those who received an offer immediately. It is important to fulfill the admission requirements on time, so carefully read the rules on the website of the admissions committee. For transfer to the budget at the university, 2 conditions are key: the entrant must first be enrolled in a contract for the relevant specialty; competitive score — from 130 points.

Priority accommodation and a discount on accommodation in student dormitories. IDP students have the right to priority accommodation in dormitories. At the same time, the university offers a discount of up to 50% of the cost of accommodation.

Professional development and retraining of IDPs

The university also actively provides educational services for improving the qualifications or retraining of IDPs through the system of state vouchers for training. Persons registered as internally displaced and unable to find a job in their specialty at their new place of residence have the opportunity to use a training voucher from the state employment service. This will allow you to improve your qualifications or learn a new profession. The maximum voucher amount is 26,840 hryvnias. According to this system of vouchers, more than 50 people from the number of IDPs were retrained at the Lviv Polytechnic and received, in particular, the new specialty "Social work" in the 2023-2024 academic year. Recruitment for such courses continues, and in the 2024-2025 academic year, it is planned to conduct advanced training for almost 100 more IDPs.

Accessibility Service for the Needs of Higher Education

To meet the needs of IDPs, the Lviv Polytechnic operates the "Accessibility Service for the Needs of Higher Education", which provides educational and social inclusion services not only to persons with disabilities or chronic diseases, but also to all internally displaced persons and their family members, military personnel and war veterans and to their family members (<https://lpnu.ua/nolimits>).

Assistance in socio-cultural adaptation, language courses

From the first days of the war (2022), the International Institute of Education, Culture and Relations with the Diaspora of the Lviv Polytechnic University in partnership with the Department of Education and Science of Lviv Regional Military Administration started the conversation club "Let's speak Ukrainian!" for internally displaced persons. Anyone aged 17 to 117 is invited to participate. Participation in the club is FREE (https://znayshov.com/News/Details/rozmovnyi_klub_hovorimo_ukrainskoiu)

Coordination of assistance of international organizations for IDPs

The University held a coordination event with stakeholders who help IDPs living in Polytechnic buildings (<https://lpnu.ua/news/v-universyteti-provely-koordinatsiyni-zakhid-zi-steikholderamy-iaki-dopomahaiut-vpo-shcho>). On January 23, 2023, a coordination event was held for the first time in the main building of the Lviv Polytechnic with the participation of such humanitarian organizations as PIN, CORE, DRC, WCK, NRC (UDOC department, ICLA SHELTER), IOM, regarding the establishment of cooperation with the university administration to improve living conditions internally displaced persons in the buildings of the Polytechnic. The organizer of the event was the Norwegian non-governmental humanitarian organization NORWEGIAN REFUGEE COUNCIL.

The development of a professional career and improve integration into a new environment

The University presented the project "Supporting the development of youth entrepreneurship among IDPs" (January 12, 2023), which will allow IDP youth to be involved in active changes in their own professional and social functioning, will contribute to the development of a professional career and improve integration into a new environment.

Career guidance measures to attract new IDP students

For IDP entrants, the Summer School of a Young Social Leader was held - a career orientation event that made it possible to attract new IDP students - immigrants from Zaporizhzhia, Vinnytsia, Dnipro, Mykolaiv (<https://lpnu.ua/news/na-kafedri-sotsiologii-ta-sotsialnoi-roboty-zavershyla-robotu-iv-litnia-shkola-molodoho>). For students, acquaintance events are held - Freshman's Week, Meetings in the professor's office, etc.

Promotion of socio-psychological adaptation and integration of IDP students and teachers in new conditions

During the opening of the library for internally displaced persons in the shelter at the Lviv Polytechnic National University, representatives of the "Youth Movement of Ukraine" organization held an interactive event on the eve of Mother's Day (15.05.2023). Activities included various games, entertainment and creativity (<https://lpnu.ua/news/u-prykhystku-dlia-vpo-pry-lvivskii-politekhniitsi-naperedodni-dnia-materi-provely-interaktyv>).

For a better understanding of the processes that ensure effective integration of IDPs into host communities, and in particular, to understand the university's capabilities in these processes, the lecturers of the Department of Sociology and Social Work took part in the UKRAINETT+ conference on social crisis management (<https://lpnu.ua/news/vykladachky-kafedry-sr-vzialy-uchast-u-konferentsii-ukrainett-z-upravlinnia-suspilnymy-kryzamy>), September 16-17, 2024 at the Business School of the Nord University (Budo, Norway). In particular, they joined the round table "Anti-migration at the local level: reflections on challenges and opportunities from the point of view of different stakeholders", which became a platform for the exchange of opinions between researchers from different countries and an important step in strengthening international scientific cooperation in the field of social crisis research and migration challenges facing Ukraine today.

IDP teachers and students are active participants in a number of international educational and scientific projects implemented with the participation of Lviv Polytechnic National University and international partners. In particular, this is the TURBO project - "University Response to Major Obstacles: Creating Resilient Higher Education for Response and Management of Social Crises", which aims to increase the resilience, readiness and speed of response of Ukrainian higher education institutions (HEIs) by building their capacity, improving competencies and exchanging experience. This project has received funding from the European Union (ERASMUS-EDU-2023-CBHE) under grant agreement No 101129315. The project manager from Lviv Polytechnic is Associate Professor Shapovalova Tetyana - an IDP teacher, former Vice-Rector for Research of Luhansk V. Dal National University. Thanks to this project, the Department of Sociology and Social Work has opened an educational and information hub "SocioSpace". This will allow for interactive training sessions for students, promote the development of professional skills and the use of modern digital tools, primarily in programs for professional retraining of internally displaced persons. <https://lpnu.ua/news/u-lvivskii-politekhniitsi-vidkryly-osvitno-informatsiinyi-khab-sotsioprostr>

Conclusions

The lack of real prospects for the cessation of hostilities and the rapid restoration of state control over all territories will result in a further increase in the scale of internal population migration. The main challenges associated with the forced displacement of citizens are manifested in the growing burden on local labor markets, the existence of problems of accommodation, employment, medical care, psychological rehabilitation, access to education, cultural and social reintegration, etc.

Through humanitarian and social crisis caused by military actions, which provoked a large number of internal displacements within the country and mass displacement abroad, HEIs are called to respond adequately and flexibly to these challenges. In particular, universities should approach the solution of this problem comprehensively, from the standpoint of a holistic (holistic) and systemic understanding of social responsibility and the principles of the "civic university". To this end, Ukrainian HEIs initiate social events or initiatives - humanitarian, psychological, organizational assistance to internally displaced persons, assistance to the military and representatives of the territorial defense, informational support of the country at various sites against Russian aggression, informing employees and students about possible projects, etc.

Universities play an important social role, on which the socio-economic and socio-cultural development of the country and society depends. The specificity of higher education lies in the fact that higher education institutions take care of science and research, being at the beginning of the innovation chain, while at the same time, new knowledge, norms, values, and models of behavior are disseminated through the university. An important function of HE as a system is to influence the formation of national identity, historical memory and the institution of citizens, which means that higher education is also an element of civil society. The HEIs are important during the war and post-war reconstruction: on the one hand, they continue to fulfill their educational function and research, which are important for economic development and the military sphere, which is especially relevant for our country. On the other hand, HE is an important institution for post-war recovery: through various forms of interaction with society, this macro-social institution is an important factor in the realization of social responsibility.

Scientists from different countries recognize the importance of social responsibility of the university, and its initiatives are perceived as a favorable tool for realizing sustainability and improving the work of universities. From a strategic point of view, the social responsibility of the university represents an opportunity for social development in all its diversity of spheres of influence, such as organizational, educational, research, social, etc.

The University has an impact on society and its economic, social and political development. It not only directly affects the future of the world in terms of training professionals and leaders, but it is also a benchmark and a social actor that can promote (or not) progress, that can create (or not) social capital, connect (or not) education bringing students closer to external social reality, which makes knowledge accessible (or not) to everyone, etc. Thus, the social environment of the University gets a certain idea about its role and ability (or not) to be a full-fledged and useful interlocutor in solving its problems.

Having substantiated a fairly universal approach to the social responsibility of universities, F. Vallaeys proposed its definition as: "the ethical policy of university quality management, which aims to harmonize its four processes (management, teaching, research, expansion) with the mission of the university, its values and social obligations solutions by achieving institutional consistency, transparency and dialogic participation of the entire university community (authorities, students, teachers, administrators) with several social subjects interested in the good performance of the university and in need of it, for the effective transformation of society in the direction of solving their problems isolation, inequality and stability"(Vallaeys, 2007, P. 5).

In the state of war unleashed by Russia against Ukraine, not only the liquidation of Ukrainian statehood, but also the physical destruction of the Ukrainian people and their identity was under threat. Ukrainian society is consolidating, as this is the basic guarantee of its self-preservation. The demand for social responsibility in it is significantly increasing. This requires domestic universities to strengthen proactive and reactive social responsibility. In the conditions of the war, the need for the implementation of social projects and programs is sharply increasing, both to preserve the integrity and ensure the functioning of the HEIs itself, and to maintain the vital activities of the communities to which they belong. The state of war in society sharply worsens the conditions for ensuring the proper quality of higher education, which is a basic component of the social responsibility of universities.

It is also obvious that in crisis conditions, in periods when society is undergoing significant trials and transformations, the social role of higher education institutions is growing. This regularity has become especially pronounced now in Ukraine, in the conditions of war. The social role of domestic universities is no less critical at the stage of post-war reconstruction of Ukraine. That is why it is important to ensure the readiness of higher education institutions of Ukraine to fulfill their social role, taking into account such characteristics as existing characteristics / activity / experience of universities as a basis / foundation for movement in the direction of the Civic University paradigm.

Lviv Polytechnic belongs to the top universities of Ukraine: According to the criteria of U- Multirank (U-Multirank. URL: <https://www.umultirank.org/about/u-multirank/the-project/>) it is in the fourth place in Ukraine. U-Multirank is a multidimensional rating of higher education institutions that evaluates the activities of universities in 5 areas: 1) teaching and learning; 2) research (research); 3) knowledge transfer (knowledge transfer); 4) international orientation (international orientation); 5)

regional engagement. The latter is directly related to the social mission of universities. The level of manifestation of the social direction of the National University "Lviv Polytechnic" is assessed as moderate, which indicates the transition from situational to systemic influence and interaction of the University and the community (Балджи, Власова, Калашнікова, Ковтунець, Литовченко, Оржель, Рябченко, 2022, р. 46).

Recommendations

To create and strengthen the "University-Community" system in Ukraine, training at the OP Social work and practices for solving the specified problems would create a single complex of mutual enrichment of knowledge, skills and technologies. The leading role in the social integration of IDPs in the new conditions of life should be played by the HEI as an institution that traditionally, in addition to educational tasks, also plays a socio-cultural, civic-societal significance for many social groups. Thanks to interaction with other components of the social and cultural space, the university becomes an open social environment. The latter not only initiates mutual enrichment with the social and educational influence of cultural, leisure, and social protection institutions, but also becomes a certain central center for the generation and implementation of social programs for adaptation, integration, and identification of the social subjectivity of forced migrants.

The analysis of the needs and problems of IDPs from among full-time students, teachers of HEIs, as well as students of advanced training courses at the university for persons from among IDPs, and the responses of Ukrainian universities to the challenges of the humanitarian and social crisis caused by the war in Ukraine, obtained by conducting different research formats. Each of the conducted activities and applied research methods complemented the other and thus made it possible to obtain a comprehensive, holistic picture.

We managed to identify the multitude of problems faced by IDP students and teachers at universities, in host communities, at a new place of study and work. It was also determined how the process of social adaptation and integration of IDPs into the host territorial and university communities takes place. It has been established that not all social and socio-psychological problems of both IDPs students and teachers have been resolved. The process of solving these problems can be influenced by university communities - the administration, its divisions or departments and individual services (Department of Personnel Development and Advanced Training, Research Department, Center for International Education, Project Office, Educational and Methodological Department, Scientific and Technical Library and others). However, universities have not yet done enough to realize their social function.

Proposals for the management of the university and the administrative body to improve the level of meeting the needs of IDP students and teachers:

- it is expedient to create a separate information-consultation-coordination unit that will take care of issues of social and educational inclusion of IDP students and teachers, to ensure interaction between various structural and functional parts of the university and the community to solve actual problems of IDPs;

- help in social adaptation and integration into the university and wider territorial community should be defined as part of the internal policy of the university and the strategy of the development of HEIs for the future.

The potential of social work in solving the problems of IDPs, in our opinion, is quite powerful. Since the problem of internally displaced persons from the east of Ukraine has a complex nature, which is connected with the presence of both objective and subjective factors in it, social work with this category of the population should be integrative in nature, include the entire set of necessary measures, ensure effective performance of basic functions in their harmonious combination.

Social workers act as subjects of social work. The purpose of working with the families of IDPs is to:

- ensure the availability of a range of services for internally displaced persons and their families;
- providing assistance in acquiring the skills of adequate behavior in a new social environment, a part of which is the immediate environment;
- minimization of negative consequences or even complete resolution of family or individual problems;
- elimination of difficulties associated with adaptation to new environmental conditions;
- provision of effective humanitarian services to improve the quality of life of families.

Accordingly, in the training of social workers under Social Work program, a course should be provided that would touch directly on these tasks.

In the retraining programs of social workers, provide for further holding of such focus groups in order to promptly monitor changes in the needs of IDPs, conflict zones and methods of solving such problems.

In social work with IDPs (and in the preparation of courses for training and retraining of social workers), it is paramount to work in several directions:

1. Practical social work (work with a specific person or group of people in need of social assistance).
2. Organizational work (organization of social service work, development of specific activity programs, etc.).
3. Outreach work with IDPs, which is aimed at establishing and maintaining contact with those target audiences with whom effective work is not carried out either by existing services or by means of traditional channels of information by visiting gathering places and (or) residence of its representatives.

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